

Multi-User 6G Radio Access Networks: THz Fiber Wireless X-Haul of a Multi-Beam Millimeter Wave Antenna

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Abstract— The rise of the 6G era promotes massive broadband wireless connectivity in dense multi-user networks, equipped with flexible X-haul transport schemes. This work presents the first experimental demonstration of the end-to-end signal flow of a flexible THz Fiber Wireless (FiWi) X-haul that aggregates and simultaneously transports the multiple Intermediate Frequency over Fiber (IFoF) streams of a mmWave Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) antenna on a single wavelength in the analog domain. Specifically, the FiWi X-haul transmission relies on a pair of 150 GHz antennas with 256 radiating elements placed after a 7km-long fiber spool, acting as a THz wireless bridge that provides flexible, seamless last mile connectivity. In turn, mmWave access in the Radio Access Network (RAN) segment is provided by means of a cascaded MIMO Phased Array Antenna (PAA) hosting three analog Intermediate Frequency (IF) input ports with microwave filtering and RF beamsteering. The proposed THz FiWi multi-IFoF X-haul link transports three different V-band user beams, each supporting a 250Mbd QPSK signal with individual analog RF beamsteering anywhere within a 90° sector, mapping each beam at a different transport IF. The proposed system distributes a 1.5 Gb/s data rate in three steerable beams anywhere in the 90° field of view of the MIMO antenna or to unleash a peak aggregate rate of >10 Gb/s at a single beam-direction, forming a flexible THz multi-IFoF X-haul of a multi-beam mmWave antenna on a single-wavelength and a promising roadmap for future multi-user 6G RANs.

Index Terms—6G, Analog Radio-over-Fiber, Beamsteering, Cascaded IF-over-Fiber, Fiber-Wireless, MIMO, Mobile Fronthaul, Phased Array Antenna, THz, V-band.

I. INTRODUCTION

The need for broadband connectivity has been driving a frantic scaling of wireless traffic capacities in the Radio Access Network (RAN) exhibiting a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 30% [1], spurring various innovative network services, such as enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB)

communications, Virtual/Augmented Reality (AR/VR), Internet of Everything (IoE) etc. This trend is expected to continue in the era of 6G, predicting even more demanding metrics in the context of the IMT 2030 Framework [2] that forecast aggregate data rates of 100Gb/s-1Tb/s to the antenna, extreme user coverage with 1Gb/s data-rate everywhere, massive connectivity and traffic densities with mmWave and THz antennas [3]. Eventually, the rise of dense multi-user 6G environments poses two main challenges [4]: i) addressing the extreme coverage by antennas that deliver multiple wireless streams with data-rates >1Gb/s in their field of view and ii) developing efficient transport and signal processing to handle the data-traffic without excessive bandwidth overheads or multiple parallel transceiver.

Towards providing extreme broadband user-coverage, multi-element antenna arrays in the higher carrier-frequencies in the millimeter-wave (mmWave) range are actively being promoted in the RAN [5]. Specifically, mmWave frequencies in the V-band/60 GHz benefit from a 7 GHz-wide contiguous available spectrum towards facilitating broader channel bandwidths, with 3GPP rel. 17 standardizing the band n263 at 57-71 GHz with User Equipment (UE) channel bandwidths up to 2 GHz [6]. Latest mmWave Phased Array Antennas (PAA) and Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) antenna prototypes integrate radiating numerous elements from 32 to 256 [7], promoting beam-shaping and steering towards larger antenna gains, unravelling multi-beam broadband access points and small cell architectures for multi-user 6G RANs [8]-[10].

On the other hand, towards facilitating flexible last mile connectivity of the X-haul (fronthaul/midhaul/backhaul) transport to the antenna site, THz frequencies operating in the range between 0.1–1 THz have emerged as a promising candidate-solution for seamless Fiber Wireless (FiWi) links with reduced installation times and deployment requirements [11],[12]. Global efforts in the THz domain are constantly

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Fig. 1. Conceptual schematic of a next generation (6G) Fiber Wireless network architecture deploying two typical cases of THz TxRx antenna technologies as efficient fiber-equivalent infrastructure: (a) THz Fiber Wireless links for Fixed Wireless Access (FWA) scenarios and (b) THz Fiber Wireless Fiber bridge for fronthauling of multi-beam mmWave MIMO antenna in high capacity and high user-density hotspot environments.

pushing towards realizing THz carrier generation and advanced modulation techniques with reduced phase noise [13], aiming to release fiber-equivalent wireless transmission capacities. Recent developments of THz FiWi links for 5G/6G have achieved groundbreaking single channel line rates of 71.4 Gb/s [14], 103.2 Gb/s [15] and 240 Gb/s [16] and real time communications between 100 Gb/s transceiver antennas [17].

Nevertheless, the introduction of THz and mmWave antennas in 6G RANs necessitates efficiently interconnecting the several distant remote radio and antenna units by means of optical fiber, pushing tremendous load on the shoulders of the X-haul network to transport and process the aggregated radiofrequencies [4]. Traditional Digital Radio over Fiber (DRoF) schemes, such as CPRI/e-CPRI, utilize either low-layer functional splits with prohibitively high data-rates for high-carrier frequencies or some form of packetized traffic with demanding and energy-consuming processing at the antenna site [18],[19]. In contrast, Analog Radio-over-Fiber (ARoF) and Intermediate Frequency over Fiber (IFoF) offer a promising

spectrally-efficient transport scheme, inherently suited with flexible last mile FiWi X-haul connectivity, as they allow loading multiple radio signals directly on an optical carrier [19]. Recent high capacity ARoF/IFoF mmWave X-haul links have achieved to unravel up to 1Tb/s CPRI equivalent rates in fiber setups [20] or capacities up to 24 Gb/s in FiWi Point-to-Point (PtP) configurations, yet between horn antennas [21]-[24].

Towards scaling from unitary PtP links to multi-user environments in Point-to-MultiPoint (PtMP) architectures with several individual mmWave beams, various forms of multiplexing are introduced in the X-haul network, including Wavelength Division Multiplexing [25],[26], Space Division Multiplexing in multi-core fibers [27], Mode Division Multiplexing [28], Polarization Multiplexing [29] or even combinations of those that maximized parallel traffic capacities [30]. However, such multiplexing schemes so far rely only on two static PtP end-points in fiber-transmission setups or FiWi configurations between horn antennas at a single beam-direction, with IFoF traffic shared among many parallel optical

TABLE I: STATE OF THE ART DEVELOPMENTS OF PHASED ARRAY ANTENNAS AROUND 150GHZ CARRIER FREQUENCY IN WIRELESS MULTI-BEAM PROTOTYPE CONFIGURATIONS AND FIBER WIRELESS X-HAUL LINKS FOR 6G RANS

Ref.	Carrier Freq.	Wireless lengths	Data Rate	Mod. formats	Bandwidth Symbol Rate	Fiber length	Wireless hops	No. beams	No. Users and Beamsteering
[31]	140 GHz	15 cm	200 Gb/s	32-QAM	30 GHz	-	1	4	4 - Yes $\pm 45^\circ$
[32]	150 GHz	34 cm	16 Gb/s	QPSK	2 GHz	-	1	4	4 - Yes $\pm 30^\circ$
[15]	123 GHz	180 m	103 Gb/s	4096-QAM	15 GHz	meters	1	1	0 - No
[33]	140 GHz	30 cm	24 Gb/s	64-QAM	7.5 GHz	-	1	1	1 - Yes $\pm 60^\circ$
[34]	137 GHz	30 cm	2x42 Gb/s	64-QAM	10.2 GHz	-	1	1	1 - Yes $\pm 45^\circ$
[35]	135 GHz	3 m	60 Gb/s	PAM-8	20 GHz	10 km	1	1	0 - No
[36]	141 GHz	20 cm	352 Gb/s	16-QAM	22 GHz	25 km	1	1	0 - No
[37]	152 GHz	3.1 m	1 Tb/s	64-QAM	24 GHz	10 km	1	1	0 - No
[38]	137 GHz	60 cm	184 Gb/s	QPSK	46 GHz	80 km	1	1	0 - No
[39]	135 GHz	4.6 km	23.1 Gb/s	64-QAM	6 GHz	10 km	1	1	0 - No
[40]	202 GHz	-	100 Gb/s	64-QAM	30 GHz	20 km	2	1	1 - No
This Work	156 GHz	50 cm	10.6 Gb/s	64-QAM	6 GHz	7 km	2	3	3 - Yes $\pm 45^\circ$

transceivers, thus not aggregating multiple individual beams of multi-user environments. To this end, only a few multi-user FiWi X-haul demonstrations have achieved to demonstrate the aggregation of multiple different beams of PtMP network architectures, either by introducing o-e-o conversions and DSP processing for channel de-aggregation at an intermediate X-haul node [30] or inserting optical demultiplexers [25] of four completely parallel WDM FiWi links, that require additional hardware complexity and latency overheads. Table I summarized the recent state of the art developments of PAAs around 150GHz carrier frequency used in wireless multi-beam prototype configurations and Fiber Wireless X-haul links for 6G RANs, where it can be seen that latest prototypes have recently started to support multi-beam operation at up to four beams in wireless links only [31] 46 GHz bandwidth in static, point-to-point only FiWi configurations [38], as well as cascaded FiWi THz mmWave links with only one-beam and without any beamsteering [40]. The current work combines for the first time FiWi THz X-hauling of a mmWave PAA, along with three mmWave mobile terminals anywhere within the 90o degree sector for multi-user mmWave RAN environments.”

In this work, we experimentally present for the first time to our knowledge a flexible THz FiWi multi-IFoF X-haul of a mmWave MIMO antenna, that simultaneously aggregates and transports three individual beams on three IF at the same wavelength. The current work extends our preliminary work in [31] with identical modulation formats for the three beams by presenting the end-to-end signal flow, while introducing variable traffic and scalable symbol rates for each beam. Initially, we present the characterization of the THz and mmWave antenna units that operate in the 146-165 GHz and 58.5-61.5 GHz with a 10-dB bandwidth of 11.2 GHz and 2.7 GHz respectively, allowing to fit the transmission of the three broadband channels in the cascaded Wireless-Fiber-Wireless (Wi-FiWi) link, filtering one of them for evaluation purposes. The proposed X-haul architecture is thoroughly benchmarked with QPSK signals with 1.5 Gb/s rate, supporting mmWave beamsteering at up to $\pm 45^\circ$, fiber lengths up to 7km and a dynamic power range of 7.5 dB, thus satisfying the respective KPIs for the user rate anywhere in the antenna field of view. Finally, variable user traffic with modulation formats up to 64-QAM and baudrates up to 900 Mbd are presented, after replacing the MIMO antenna with a broadband horn antenna. The current work forms the first demonstration of a single wavelength THz FiWi multi-IFoF X-haul of a multi-beam mmWave access point, forming a promising hardware roadmap for future, high-density, multi-user 6G networks.

II. ARCHITECTURE AND END-TO-END RF CHAIN

Our proposed network architecture is depicted in Fig. 1(a), aiming to tackle the above challenges of transporting multiple individual beams of massive connectivity on a single, spectrally efficient and flexible THz FiWi multi-IFoF X-haul link, simultaneously catering either for high capacity THz backhaul links or fronthaul transport of multi-beam mmWave MIMO PAAs. The THz links can provide last mile connectivity as a seamless wireless extension of the fiber between two fixed end-

points [12], e.g. a rooftop-to-rooftop link, with fiber equivalent capacities [13]-[16]. On the other hand, the multi-beam mmWave MIMO PAA can host different input ports that perform de-aggregation of the multi-IFoF X-haul streams and channel-selection prior to beamforming and steering that direct each individual stream to a different user.

As depicted in the proposed signal flow in Fig. 1 (b), the user data is loaded on high frequency carriers, e.g. THz or mmWave, exclusively for broadband wireless transmission, while channel filtering and de-aggregation signal processing are performed in lower, microwave sub-6 GHz frequencies. Initially, the architecture relies on a pool of DSP-enabled analog IFoF transceivers that are placed at a centralized network location such as an edge-network equipment that hosts a pool of baseband unit processing functionalities. The DSP enabled IFoF transceivers can synthesize a proper radio waveform and digitally upconvert it to an IF. The digitally synthesized IF signal can then be imprinted on an optical carrier using simple Intensity Modulation/Direct Detection (IM/DD) techniques to drive the operation of an optical transceiver, as e.g. an Mach Zehnder Interferometer (MZI) or externally modulated laser, generating an Optical Dual Side-Band (ODSSB) IFoF signal. After the optoelectrical (o/e) conversion at the PD, the obtained IF signal is amplified, followed by RF mixing at the THz antenna for up-conversion and wireless transmission.

Moving on to the fronthaul link, the THz signal is again down-converted to the IF, and optionally amplified or loaded to an additional optical subcarrier of the cascaded fiber segment, before being fed to the multi-beam mmWave access point. There, the frequencies of the three radio signals can be de-aggregated using low-cost microwave filters, so as to be separated into three single frequency band signals. Each of the three signals is then propagated towards the PAA, featuring 1:N channels with analog phase shifting, amplification and RF up-conversion stages for directional wireless transmission at mmWave frequencies. At the end point, the Rx of the client mobile terminal shall receive the radiated mmWave signal and sequentially down-convert it to the IF and baseband (or directly to the baseband) to extract the actual data information, after applying the reverse DSP stages used at the Tx side.

The current work describes the development of all the FiWi transceiver components to realize the above vision of a flexible and efficient FiWi THz X-haul of multi-user mmWave networks, along with detailed experimental characterization of their bandwidths and data transmission for the end-to-end operation. For the demonstration of the proposed end-to-end Wi-FiWi link, an experimental setup was implemented, comprising three main transmission stages, namely (i) a fixed PtP THz link, (ii) a fiber-optical transmission segment and (iii) a V-band stage equipped with IF filtering and RF beamsteering.

III. THZ AND MMWAVE TRANSCIEVER ANTENNAS

This section contains a detailed description of the novel transceiver antennas operating in the THz band and the V-band. The THz link is based on a pair of high-gain antennas, to compensate for the losses of the higher carrier frequency, which are depicted in Fig. 2 (a). The antennas feature a flat radiating

Fig. 2. (a) Picture of the V-band PAA Tx antenna system, consisting of a Control PCB (left) and a Tile Feed PCB (right), (b) close-up picture of the front panel of the PAA Tx antenna and (c) experimental characterization of the 3-dB and 10-dB bandwidth for the V-band wireless transmission, (d) Picture of the THz Tx and Rx antennas, (e) close up picture of the THz Rx antenna front panel and (f) experimental characterization of the 3-dB and 10-dB bandwidth for the THz FiWi link.

front-panel with 256 radiating elements, as shown in the close zoomed in photo in Fig. 2 (b). The design of the antenna front panel relies on a radiating slot antenna array configuration that formulate an Electromagnetic Bandgap (EBG) [42], which results in an antenna radiation pattern with 30 dBi gain, while squeezing the 16×16 slots in a thin planar frontend interface of only $40 \times 40 \times 8$ mm³ dimension. The high antenna gain allows placing the THz antennas at a distance of 0.5m at a fixed steering angle of 0°. The THz carrier-frequency link is initially characterized by feeding a single tone for wireless transmission and tuning the carrier frequency across 145-165 GHz frequency range. As it is shown in shown Fig. 2 (c), the THz link supports a 3-dB bandwidth of 6 GHz and a 10-dB bandwidth of 11.2 GHz.

The THz radiating frontend is also equipped with RF up-conversion and down-conversion stages to generate a complete packaged antenna Tx and Rx assembly respectively. The RF mixing stage is capable of multiplying an external Local Oscillator (LO) signal by $\times 12$ times, before being fed to the Tx and Rx antenna, generating the 156 GHz RF carrier. On the other hand, the I/\bar{I} and Q/\bar{Q} data input ports of the Tx antenna are fed with a radio signal. The THz receiver antenna features a THz Low Noise Amplifier (LNA) with 25 dB gain, placed directly after antenna structure to increase the Rx sensitivity, followed by the down-conversion stage that generates the IF signal. The Tx THz antenna assembly is provided with a 5 V and 145 mA supply, resulting in a power consumption of 0.725 W, while the Rx THz antenna assembly consumes 0.845 W.

For the mmWave (V-band) access point, the proposed setup features a multi-antenna PAA Tx system with three RF input ports with channel selection and analog RF-beamsteering for mmWave wireless transmission at different beams/streams. The signal entering one of the three RF input ports of the mmWave access points is initially filtered by analog microwave filtering elements, before the upconversion and transmission over the air. Each of the three different branches features a different passband filtering stage based on commercially available passive microwave components, to allow only one of the IF signals to pass and drop the rest of the two IF-bands.

The V-band Tx antenna system is comprised of a Control Printed Circuit Board (Control PCB) and a Tile Feed PCB board, as shown in Fig. 2 (d). The antenna system features a $\times 6$ multiplication stage of an external LO that is mixed with an IF input signal between 0.6 GHz and 5.65 GHz for RF-upconversion and radiation in the frequency range between 57 and 64 GHz. In turn, the V-band antenna board at the radiating front-panel features a PAA of 32 radiating elements depicted in Fig. 2 (b), supporting analog RF beamsteering anywhere within a 120° angle [43]. The antenna board integrates a 1:32 splitter with 32-channels of ϕ -phase shifting elements and LNAs that each feed a 6 dBi dipole, capable of tuning the amplitude and phase of each radiating element, to perform beamforming and beam steering, as described in detail in [43]. The Tx V-band antenna assembly is provided with a 5.3 V and 635 mA supply, resulting in 3.365W power consumption.

The characterization of the bandwidth supported by the V-link PAA is depicted in Fig. 2 (f). Measurements of the 3-dB and 10-dB bandwidth are performed to evaluate the supported channel bandwidth, by feeding the Tx antenna with a single IF tone, tuned from 3.25 GHz up to 6 GHz, resulting in sweeping the carrier frequency from 58.75 to 61.5 GHz. The measurements of the RF power with a Signal Analyzer reveal a 3-dB bandwidth of 0.95 GHz and a 10-dB bandwidth of 2.7 GHz. The PAA has been thoroughly characterized in various beamsteering scenarios and FiWi X-haul configurations in [43], achieving up to 120 degree Field of View, transmission of up to 32-QAM modulation format and linearity characterization in two tone measurements with a third order Intercept Point (IIP3) of 4.8 dBm in FiWi configurations.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The transmission path is divided in three stages, the THz stage which consists of the fixed PtP THz wireless link, the optical transmission stage, and the V-band stage with RF beamsteering as shown in Fig. 3. The transmitted signal is synthesized by a Keysight Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG). Both single band and three band radio signals are

Fig. 3. Experimental setup of the End-to-End (WiFiWi) proposed system comprising three transmission stages, a fixed PtP THz link, a fiber-optical transmission segment and a V-band link with RF beamsteering.

generated, and upconverted to an IF subcarrier between 0.6 GHz and 5.65 GHz with an 800 mV voltage swing. The THz transmitter and receiver, previously described in section III, are provided with an external 13 GHz LO signal of 7 dBm average power for the up-conversion and down-conversion. The I/\bar{I} and Q/\bar{Q} data input ports of the Tx antenna are fed with the radio signal generated by the AWG. The final wireless signal is transmitted over the air across a 0.5m link-distance at carrier frequencies between 156.6 GHz and 161.6 GHz. After the wireless transmission, the signal is received by the Rx antenna assembly, that generates the IF signal output.

After the THz over the air transmission, the received signal is propagated at the optical transmission stage. The IF signal is amplified by an SHF amplifier, to drive an MZI LiNbO₃ modulator with a $V\pi$ of 4 V. The MZI modulator is fed by a Continuous Wavelength (CW) optical signal at 1550 nm provided by a Distributed Feedback (DFB) Laser Source with a saturation output power of 16 dBm, which is tuned through an inline Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA). The generated optical IFoF signal is then transmitted through a Single-Mode Fiber (SMF) spool with a fiber length of 7 km, before entering a 10 GHz PIN Photoreceiver (PD) for o/e conversion. The signal transmission up to this point is experimentally characterized in the next section and is further referred to as the THz FiWi link.

The multi-band signal is then propagated at the V-band stage of the setup. Here, the multi-antenna PAA system initially de-aggregates the three so-far Subcarrier-Multiplexed IF-bands into three separate signals and subsequently performs individual RF-beamsteering and mmWave wireless transmission at different beams. To achieve this, the RF signal exiting the PD is amplified by an RF amplifier with a gain of 25 dB and sequentially connected to a passive RF splitter, whose outputs are followed by properly centered analog microwave filtering elements. As mentioned before, each of the three different branches are featuring a different passband filtering stage based on commercially available passive microwave components, that are centered at $f_1 = 4.6$ GHz for the first band, $f_2 = 5.3$ GHz for the second band and $f_3 = 5.65$ GHz for the third band.

Each of the filtered IF-bands is then fed as input at the IF input

interface of the V-band PAA Tx antenna system. The PAA is provided with an external LO signal of around 9.3 GHz and 15 dBm, which is mixed with the IF input signal between 0.6 GHz and 5.65 GHz. The wireless signal is transmitted over the air across 6 m of distance at carrier frequencies between 57 and 62 GHz. After the wireless V-band transmission, the signal is received by a portable horn receiver antenna assembly. The Rx horn antenna assembly converts the received V-band signal back to the IF signal, featuring a similar x6 down-conversion stage, that is also provided by a separate dedicated external LO signal of around 9.5 GHz. The down-converted signal is fed to a Signal Analyzer for demodulation and evaluation of the constellation diagrams and Error Vector Magnitude (EVM).

An alternative setup is also presented, where the V-band transmitter PAA is manually replaced by a compact and simpler horn antenna, as shown in Fig 4. The RF filters used in this setup are sharper and placed more sparsely, resulting in improved crosstalk. The horn antenna has a broader bandwidth of around 7 GHz, demonstrating higher aggregate traffic capacities. The antenna system also features an x6 multiplication stage of an external LO signal of 9.5 GHz and 10 dBm power. The rest of the setup remained the same.

V. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE THZ FiWi LINK

The first section of the experimental results presents detailed transmission measurements solely across the THz FiWi link for a single band and a three band transmission setup. For the single band operation, an IF centered at 2.6 GHz was selected and transmitted at different power levels and increasing modulation formats, with the results depicted in Fig. 4(a)-(c). For the evaluation of the single-band data transmission, we are using a signal of various waveforms of increasing modulation format starting from QPSK up to 64-QAM with a symbol rate of 750 MBaud with an optical input power level of -13.5 dBm. Fig. 4 (a) shows the respective constellation diagrams for transmissions in different modulation formats, including QPSK, 16-QAM, 32-QAM and 64-QAM. For each transmitted waveform, the EVM value is measured to be 7.02% for the QPSK, 5.84% for the 16-QAM, 4.74% for the 32-QAM and 5.56% for the 64-QAM, being at all cases below the respective requirements established by 3GPP [6]. The latter corresponds to a data rate of 4.5 Gb/s achieved for a single-band THz FiWi transmission. According to [44], the EVM values of 17.5% for the QPSK, 12.5% for the 16-QAM and 8% for the 64-QAM of the technical recommendations would correspond to BER values 10^{-9} , 10^{-4} and 10^{-3} respectively, while our FiWi THz channel seems to satisfy these recommendations. An estimated calculation of the Bit Error Rate from the EVM can be extracted from the work presented in [44] and [45].

Fig. 4 (b) shows the RF spectrum of the received signal after the FiWi transmission of a QPSK waveform as captured by the Signal Analyzer, exhibiting a Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) of around 25 dB. Moreover, the single band FiWi transmission of a QPSK signal is characterized in terms of signal quality and dynamic range for various power levels reaching the PD, ranging from -20 dBm to -8 dBm, while measuring the EVM

Fig. 4. Experimental results of the THz link including: (a) constellation diagrams and EVM values of QPSK, 16-QAM, 32-QAM, 64-QAM single band transmissions, (b) RF spectrum of a 750 MBd single band transmission at 2.6 GHz, (c) the dynamic optical power range of the THz FiWi link, (d) RF spectrum of a 900 MBd transmission of 3 bands at 0.6 - 2.6 - 4.6 GHz, (e) constellation diagrams and EVM values of each QPSK-band & 64-QAM-band.

value of the demodulated constellation diagram. The obtained values are depicted in Fig. 4 (c), along with the EVM requirement set by 3GPP [6]. As it can be seen, the THz FiWi link achieves acceptable EVM values for power levels above -18 dBm, achieving a dynamic range of at least 9 dBm.

After the single band FiWi transmission, a set of three-band signal transmissions are performed, including three subcarrier modulated signals, centered at an IF of 0.6 GHz for the first band, 2.6 GHz for the second band and 4.6 GHz for the third band. Each of the three bands are modulated with a QPSK or 64-QAM signal at a baud rate of 900 MBaud. The RF spectrum of the received signal, after the FiWi transmission is depicted in Fig. 4 (d), exhibiting a similar SNR of 25 dB as in the single band transmission, indicating a high signal quality for the three IFoF streams anywhere within the 6 GHz 3-dB bandwidth.

Moreover, the respective constellation diagrams of each of the three bands of the signal using the QPSK modulation format are depicted in Fig. 4 (e)-upper inset, featuring EVM values of 9.56% for the first band, 7.18% for the second band and 13.15% for the third band. On the other hand, the bottom inset of Fig. 4 (e) depicts the constellation diagrams of the three received 64-QAM modulation formats at a symbol rate of 750 MBaud for each of the three bands, exhibiting EVM values of 5.34%, 3.56% and 5.4% respectively, all being again below the required 3GPP EVM thresholds [6]. The EVM of the middle IF in Fig. 4 (e) is improved due to the placement of the middle IF frequency closer to the peak-gain of the spectrum of the FiWi THz transmission spectrum shown in Fig. 2 (c). Using the proposed three-band 64-QAM, the maximum data rate achieved

for the three-band transmission through the THz FiWi link is 4.5 Gb/s per IF-band and 13.5 Gb/s peak data traffic in total [6]. Based on the data rate of 13.5 Gb/s the estimated energy efficiency for the Tx antenna is 53.7 pJ/bit. A more detailed experimental characterization of the THz FiWi link in transmission setups of various modulation formats can be found in [12].

VI. END-TO-END THz X-HAUL LINK TO A MULTI-BEAM MM-WAVE PHASED ARRAY ANTENNA SYSTEM

For the characterization of the end-to-end THz X-haul link, the V-band mmWave Tx PAA is employed, supporting analog RF beam steering towards a portable V-band horn antenna. Fig. 5 shows the experimental results that demonstrate the proof-of-principle operation, including a three-band transmission through the THz FiWi link, followed by de-aggregation of the three IF bands and selection of one of the three IF-bands using analog microwave filter, before feeding it to the PAA.

Initially, the available end-to-end bandwidth, including the cascaded THz FiWi link and the V-band link, is characterized, by sweeping a single IF tone at the data input of the THz antenna at frequencies between 4 and 7 GHz with a 0.25 GHz step and measuring the received RF power at the output of the V-band Rx horn antenna. Fig. 5 (a) shows the spectra of the characterization of the available bandwidth, exhibiting a 3-dB bandwidth of 0.8 GHz and the 10-dB bandwidth 2.6 GHz. On the one hand, the narrower bandwidth compared to the 6 GHz of the THz link in Fig. 2 (c) owes mainly to the narrower bandwidth supported by the cascaded V-band PAA, which is roughly 0.95 GHz, while on the other hand reveals the broader bandwidth credentials of the THz FiWi X-haul link to transport larger number of V-band PAAs. Nevertheless, it complies with the channel bandwidth between 400MHz to 2,000 MHz of the n263 band at 57-71 GHz standardized by 3GPP rel. 17 [6].

Fig. 5 (b) depicts the RF spectrum of the joint three-band end-to-end transmission, when all three bands are transported through the same beam. As it can be seen, the three IF bands are centered at $f_1 = 4.6$ GHz for the first band, $f_2 = 5.3$ GHz for the second band and $f_3 = 5.65$ GHz for the third band, to fit in the bandwidth of a single beam of the PAA, while the three bands feature roughly equal power levels, after experiencing similar losses through the common end-to-end channel. In this case, each of the three IFs transports a QPSK waveform at a 250 MBaud symbol rate. Fig. 5 (c) shows the demodulated constellation diagrams of each of the three bands after the end-to-end transmission, exhibiting an EVM of 16.69% for the first band, 16.35% for the second band and 14.54% for the third band, indicating a roughly equal performance that satisfies the EVM requirement set by 3GPP [6]. The EVM of the third IF appears to be slightly improved than the EVM values of IF1 and 2, as some small saturation of the gain amplifiers of the MIMO antenna led to partial suppression of the noise-error. Although EVM is the main metric used in wireless communications, it worths to note that the achieved EVM values of 16.69%, 16.35% and 14.54% satisfy the recommended EVM values, indicating BER values lower than 10^{-9} estimated in [44] for a QPSK signal for the 3GPP recommendations. This reveals the

Fig. 5. Experimental results of the End-to-end link, including: (a) characterization of the 3-dB and 10-dB bandwidth measurements for the end-to-end link with the MIMO V-band antenna, (b) RF spectrum of a 250 MBaud 3-band transmission, and (c) respective constellation diagrams, (d) RF spectrum of the same transmission using a filter to select the first band, (e) RF filter's frequency response.

capability of the end-to-end system to deliver an aggregate capacity of 1.5 Gb/s at a single beam.

Subsequently, the next step is to demonstrate the selection of one of the three IFs for wireless transmission with individual RF beamsteering through the PAA. The three-band signal is split by a 1x3 coupling stage, after the optical transmission and the first band of $f_1 = 4.6$ GHz is filtered and selected to propagate at one of the three outputs of the coupler using an analog microwave bandpass filter prior to entering the V-band PAA, while the rest of the two bands are dropped. The spectrum of the received signal, after the filtering and wireless transmission stage is shown in Fig. 5 (d), exhibiting a suppression ratio of around 14 dB for the second (f_2) and third (f_3) IFs, owing mainly to the position of the IFs with respect to the spectral response of the passive microwave filter used during the experimentation. The filter's transfer function, recorded after feeding it with multiple densely located tones of equal power levels at its input, is shown in Fig. 5 (e), exhibiting a 3-dB and 10-dB bandwidth of 1.7 GHz and 2.4 GHz.

Despite the broad filter bandwidth, placing the center of the first band f_1 at the right part of the filter's flat top response in Fig. 5 (e) results in a 14 dB suppression ratio with a clear frequency selectivity, allowing the propagation of only the first IF f_1 to the PAA, and assigning and mapping IF f_1 to the wirelessly transmitted beam. Due to the lack of passive microwave filters for the other two IF bands, it was not possible to repeat the experiment for the other two IFs through the PAA system, which would equivalently require only centering an analog microwave filter at f_2 or f_3 for IF-per-beam assignment.

In order to fully demonstrate the beam-selectivity after

Fig. 6. Experimental results for the full evaluation of the end-to-end link, including constellation diagrams and achieved EVM values for filtered transmission (a) in different beam-steering angles and (b) at different fiber lengths, the dynamic range of the end-to-end WiFiWi link for (c) a single band and (d) a three-band transmission.

filtering of IF f_1 and assigning it to the first mmWave beam, the end-to-end link is benchmarked in RF-beamsteering setup. We increase the V-band distance between the antennas to 6 m and conduct the same multi-band transmission and filtering of the first band. Two different mmWave transmissions over the air are performed with the beam being steered either at 0° or $\pm 45^\circ$. The obtained constellation diagrams after the demodulation are shown in Fig. 6 (a), featuring EVM values of 13.35% for 0° and 14.36% for $\pm 45^\circ$. The measurements confirm an equal performance anywhere within a 90° sector ($\pm 45^\circ$), in accordance with the performance of the PAA in detailed experimental sector scanning in [43]. Moreover, it reveals an EVM improvement of 3.34% and 2.33% compared to the EVM value of 16.69% for the respective IF f_1 in the three-band transmission, despite increasing the wireless transmission distance from 1m to 6m, owing mainly to the increased amplification provided by the antenna systems to only one IF f_1 instead of being distributed in three IFs.

Moreover, in order to evaluate longer fiber-propagation scenarios, the end-to-end transmission experiment with IF filtering and RF beamsteering is repeated, after interleaving an additional 7 km-long fiber spool, appended after the existing 100 m of SMF. The constellation diagrams of the received IF signal f_1 after 100m and 7.1 km fiber propagation are shown in Fig. 6 (b), revealing an EVM penalty of only 3.46%, being below the 3GPP EVM threshold.

Finally, we evaluate the dynamic range supported by the optical transmission stage of the THz FiWi link. This is performed by tuning the losses introduced by a VOA, to tune the power levels reaching the PD ranging between -20 dBm and -8 dBm, while recording the EVM of the received signal. The results obtained for the evaluation of the dynamic range of the single band and three-band transmissions in the end-to-end WiFiWi X-haul link are presented in Fig. 6 (c) and (d) respectively. As it can be seen, for the case of the single band, the end-to-end link achieved acceptable EVM values lower than 18% across a dynamic range of at least 7.5 dB, for power levels

Fig. 7. Experimental results of the End-to-end link with Horn Tx & Rx including: (a) RF spectrum of a 900 Mbaud three-band 16-QAM transmission, and (b) respective constellation diagrams of each band, (c) frequency responses of the filters used for the de-aggregation of the three bands, (d) the respective RF spectra of each de-aggregated band and (e) constellation diagrams and EVM values for the filtered transmissions.

above -16.5 dBm, indicating only a requirement for 1.5 dB higher power due to the cascaded PAA, when compared to the THz link only shown in Fig. 4 (a). On the other hand, for the case of the three-band transmission, the link supports a dynamic range of 5.5 dB, necessitating a minimum optical power level above -14.5 dBm due to the RF power-spread in three bands.

VII. CAPACITY SCALING WITH FLEXIBLE USER RATE

In this section, we extend the experimental evaluation of the cascaded THz FiWi X-haul transport of three mmWave streams towards higher aggregate traffic capacities and flexible, variable data rates per stream, emulating a scenario with different traffic requirements per mmWave user. To achieve this, the V-band transmitter PAA is replaced by a compact, simpler horn antenna with broader bandwidth of around 7 GHz, and broader microwave RF filtering of the IFs, while leaving the rest of the setup intact.

Initially, we target transmitting a high baud rate for the same modulation format across all three bands. The three IFs are now centered at $f_1 = 0.6$ GHz for the first band, $f_2 = 2.6$ GHz for the second band and $f_3 = 4.6$ GHz for the third band, while featuring a baud rate of 900 MBaud for each band. The RF spectrum of the three bands, when transmitted together across the end-to-end link is depicted in Fig. 7 (a), revealing an average SNR of 20 dB. Moreover, the three-band data are evaluated in terms of constellations diagrams of the received signals. The constellation diagrams of each of the three bands are depicted in Fig. 7 (b), achieving EVM values of 10.85%, 9.7% and 9.97% for the first, second and third band respectively, all being below the

requirement established by 3GPP [6]. This results in an aggregate traffic capacity of 10.8 Gb/s at an antenna site [6]. The EVM of the middle IF in Fig. 7 (a) is performing slightly better than the outer two as it is closer to the peak-gain of the FiWi THz link in Fig. 2 (c).

Finally, we demonstrate the de-aggregation of the three IFs into three different streams that are filtered and sequentially transmitted through the mmWave horn-to-horn links. Specifically, the three-bands after the transmission through the THz FiWi link are fed at the 1x3 coupling stage and, each branch is connected at a different bandpass microwave RF filter to separate each IF, in order to map it to a different mmWave beam. The transfer functions for the three filters used for the de-aggregation of the three IFs are depicted in Fig. 7 (c). As it can be seen, the first filter is a low pass filter with a 1.7 GHz-wide flat top, the second filter is a sharp band pass filter with a 0.7 GHz-wide flat top and the last filter is a high-pass filter with a 1.4 GHz-wide flat top, while the spectra of the three received signals after filtering and transmissions are shown in Fig. 7(d). The first two IFs feature a clear rejection of the other two undesired frequencies, with a suppression ratio that equals the suppression of the noise level, while for the third IF, there is some residue of the second IF due to the use of a high-pass filter, that did not feature a very sharp edge.

Here, each of the IF is now modulated with a different waveform, towards demonstrating a flexible varying modulation format. The respective constellation diagrams for each waveform are presented in Fig. 7 (e), demonstrating the best data rate achieved for each IF. The captured constellation diagram of the first IF f_1 corresponds to a 750 MBaud 64-QAM signal transmission with an EVM of 7.45%, the second IF f_2 featured a 32-QAM transmission at 500 Mbaud achieving an EVM of 6.86% and the third IF f_3 included a 16-QAM at 900 MBaud achieving an EVM of 10.98%. Using the above symbol rates, the achieved user data rates corresponded to 4.5 Gb/s, 2.5 Gb/s and 3.6 Gb/s respectively transmitted for the three different mmWave beams, resulting in 10.6 Gb/s aggregate capacity, while still meeting the 3GPP EVM requirement [6].

Although the presented measurements clearly reveal the capability of the proposed system to transport user rates >1Gb/s anywhere within the RAN, the number of users and peak-aggregates data rates were limited by the mere 6GHz bandwidth of the FiWi THz links. Simply by replacing the utilized antenna with state of the art transceiver antenna prototypes with up to 46 GHz [38] and utilizing the presented 750 Mbd 64-QAM signal depicted in Fig. 8(e), that can fit a 4.5 Gb/s per channel within a 1GHz user-bandwidth, the estimated aggregate data rate would be 207 Gb/s distributed across 46 user-terminals, i.e. slightly more than to the data rate latest antenna transceiver prototypes in advanced BiCMOS platforms [32], paving the way for truly multi-user 6G RANs.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The current work presents the first end-to-end experimental demonstration of a FiWi THz X-haul of a multi-beam mmWave PAA with individual RF beamsteering for up to three streams, while the data-traffic of three users is aggregated on a single optical carrier, in view of emerging 6G RANs. The proposed architecture relies on two antenna technologies, namely a THz

antenna with 256 radiating elements and a mmWave MIMO antenna system with three 32-element PAAs. The flexibility of the proposed architecture demonstrated in two scenarios, namely a multi-user transmission with 0.5 Gb/s data rate per beam anywhere in the 90° field of view of the mmWave PAA and a FiWi transmission towards a single beam direction with peak aggregate capacity of >10 Gb/s, meeting the respective KPIs for the networks beyond 5G and forming a promising technology roadmap for next generation THz/mmWave 6G networks with massive, broadband connectivity.

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